

AGAINST SUSTAINABILITY AS A PRIME DESIGN DRIVER

Walter A. Aprile,
Delft University of Technology.
w.a.aprile@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

Over the last decades, sustainability has ensconced itself in design discourse. We can easily find websites, textbooks and MSc programs in design with a focus on sustainability. There are very few companies, including oil, car and mining concerns, that do not claim to have a strong interest for sustainability.

But how do we go beyond the green and blue logos and the fetishistic use of certain materials? Sustainability, when closely examined, reveals itself to be a controversial word for a focus and a set of practices that are neither without risks nor without costs. Perhaps efficiency, while much more humble, would be a better guiding light for designers.

Keywords: sustainability, opportunity costs, development.

INTRODUCTION

Practitioners of Design and Architecture in the last century and a half have had to position themselves on an axis that goes from effective solvers of technical problems to thinkers able to attack large problems; problems such as workers' and immigrants' living conditions (manifested as urban and domestic squalor) or, more recently, inequalities in the worldwide distribution of wealth. Schools of design willing to tackle large problems frequently have had Socialist overtones, but in recent years there have been developments away from central planning and towards various forms of participatory design (Schuler and Namioka 1993) Design for sustainability can be seen as a recent development in a multi-decade line of thought that has its deep roots in William Morris' design and social criticism and in the Bauhaus. In more recent years, Pauline Madge argued (Madge 1997) that there have been

three waves, namely "green design", "eco design" and "sustainable design" characterized by a progressive broadening of concerns: sustainability, compared with green design or eco design, opens up the design space to include not only people, objects, building and cities but also the totality of Earth and human culture.

We find three major problems with the notion of sustainability:

1. its definition is loose and it tends to push the designers into difficult territories
2. it is hard to apply *a priori*
3. it is impossible to verify *a posteriori*

In our exploration of sustainability as a design driver, we have found many useful examples in "You can't just blame the crocodile" (van der Sanden 2007), a collection of rather unvarnished case reports subtitled "Delft engineers travel into sustainability".

DEFINITIONS

One current definition of sustainability as a design driver implies the broadest possible perspective, in space and in time: (Ehrenfeld 2008) defines sustainability as "the *possibility* that humans and other life will *flourish* on the Earth *forever*". Ehrenfeld is particularly interesting for us because he looks specifically at the designer's responsibilities. Sustainability is frequently mixed up in practice and education with *sustainable development*. In the 1980 World Conservation Strategy (IUCN 1980) sustainable (economic) development is achieved through the conservation of living resources, without making a further link to wider social and economic issues (Baker 2006). The turning point for the field was the 1987 UN Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development. The document states that "sustainable development is development that meets the needs of

the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (Brundtland 1987) and links tightly economy, society and the environment. The Brundtland definition, as it is frequently cited, has achieved authoritative status: in the rest of this paper we will use the Brundtland and the Ehrenfeld definitions.

The Brundtland definition goes on to outline two important concepts, namely needs and limitations

"[...] in particular the essential needs of the world's poor, to which overriding priority should be given, and [...] the idea of limitations imposed by the state of technology and social organization on the environments ability to meet present and future needs."

From the very beginnings of the notion, sustainability has been a concept mixed with sustainable development.

NEEDS

The word "needs" in this context is an infinitely flexible rhetorical tool, particularly when coupled with "the poor", shapeless huddled masses of humanity, for whose "needs" planners and designers work.

Of course, since we are designers, we know exactly what their needs are, perhaps according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Maslow, Frager et al. 1987) .

Anybody who has ever met the "poor" knows that they are actually a set of humans with their own agendas, their tools and their ideas of what their needs and, perhaps more germanely, their desires are.

Examples of the great differences in the living conditions, desires and needs of the World's "poor" can be found in "Arrival Cities" (Sanders 2011) a book that walks through 20 different cases of slums and manages to discern some fine distinctions between slums that work and slums that fail, slums that are the way to a better individual future and slums that act as social traps.

If there is something common in the voices of the "poor", it is a sense of agency: their slum-dwelling condition is seen as temporary, a step on the road to individual prosperity. If one wanted to evaluate the sustainability of any slum in the world, what would be the worth of the middle-class citizens it manages to produce?

EXCEPTIONALISM

Frequently texts about sustainability take an *exceptionalist* view of the current state of the world, namely that we are on the brink of disaster. We have been on the brink of disaster for quite a while now: we don't need to go back before Malthus to fill a long list of prophets of doom that reaches to today. That apocalypse has not happened according to previsions is -obviously- no guarantee that it will not happen eventually. At the same time, the constant failure of these previsions, usually because of an underestimation of human ingenuity, is something that gives hope for the future.

What is worse is that the average industrial designer does not have a way to decide whether the current batch of dire warnings is valid or not. In a way, for every Ehrlich

"The battle to feed all of humanity is over. In the 1970s hundreds of millions of people will starve to death in spite of any crash programs embarked upon now."

(Ehrlich 1968) it is possibly to find a Lomborg

"We are not running out energy or natural resources. There will be more and more food per head of the world's population. Fewer and fewer people are starving [...] Mankind's lot has actually improved in terms of practically every measurable indicator."

(Lomborg 2001) p. 4 that has apparently reasonable counterclaims.

Another side of exceptionalism is that "what applied to me does not apply to you". This has the odd consequence that developed countries are advising everybody else to do as they say, not as they do or have done in the past. Oddly, the UK, the US,

France, Spain, Italy and all those countries that usually fall under the loose category of developed world did not develop through processes driven by sustainability. You could easily point out various phases in their separate and varied development processes where a cavalier disregard for sustainability reigned.

Exceptionalism is the underpinning for this consequence: since the present time is radically different from the past, development recipes that worked in the past cannot be applied now. By the same token, there is no more room for technological optimism. This stands in contradiction with contemporary histories of technology and invention (Basalla 1988) that show that we have never "run out" of technology: at every moment a diverse mixture of old and new technologies (Edgerton 2007) is in action, guaranteeing so far a constant stream of innovation.

ENCHANTMENT

Max Weber coined the concept of "disenchantment": the process by which modern and secular Western society, comes to value scientific understanding of phenomena higher than belief and goals are reached through rationally designed processes. Many sustainability projects, though, succumb to the enchantment of the developing world, in particular to its countryside, villages and subsistence farming. This is also odd, considering that in the developed world the near-disappearance of subsistence farming, the growing urbanization of the population and development itself went hand in hand.

Every time a designer engages in designing for subsistence farmers, he is supporting a mode of life that, so far, has failed to guarantee prosperity, development and in many cases the simple survival of its practitioners.

Enchantment is also a prism through which to look at the developing world: a place inhabited by mysterious people, alternatively simple and complex, crazy and wise but ultimately deserving of being saved by the sustainable development practitioner. In the essay that lends the title to the book, M. Poolman in (van der Sanden 2007) starts by asking herself, why did a small village water

reservoir collapse. To summarize, it turns out that the village people were not using the reservoir for farming, hence very rationally they did not maintain it. In another essay in the same volume, W. A. van Winden is surprised that their local partners in Mozambique are apathetic: and further on, in a completely naïve reveal he states that

I feel guilty about romanticizing poverty when I suddenly find myself imagining with horror that one day, thanks to our billions in development aid, this could be a neat new-build estate, with houses furnished by Ikea and family saloons parked outside, inhabited by hardworking people who dream of... an uncomplicated life in a little hut in a far-off country.

As a matter of fact, romanticizing poverty is exactly what is done in this text. So far, nobody has managed to combine a country of little huts with universal health care, long life expectancy, freedom and the general advantages of development. Enchanted people cannot change or evolve fundamentally, or the enchantment would fade. We suspect that this is what leads designers to gadget thinking: after all, if the people cannot change it is impossible to suggest systemic solutions. Quick fixes of the product type (as opposed to the service or infrastructure types) arise, like the PeePoo bag (Vinnerås, Hedenkvist et al. 2009), powered by the assumption the slum inhabitants in Kenya will never manage to have "real" sanitation. This is another form of "what applied to me does not apply to you": examining the history of sanitation in the Western world, you can find many alternatives and intermediate steps on the millennia-long way to contemporary systems of sewers and depurators. These alternatives have already been tried and studied: to ignore them and present a fancy plastic bag as a solution is rather disingenuous and inefficient.

A DIFFICULT ASSESSMENT

One could argue that attacking sustainability because of its vagueness of definition is unfair: after all, we are perfectly happy to expend resources,

including human lives, in the service of equally elusive concepts such as freedom, human rights and democracy. Somewhat analogously to Kant's regulative ideas, we accept that there are guiding ideas, like "democracy", that are useful as conceptual beacons, even if nowhere in the world you can find a pure, fully achieved democracy - even supposing we could agree on a good definition of democracy.

Is sustainability then a good guiding idea? And when should it exercise its guiding role for the designer? Should this be a priori, a posteriori or during the work?

The main difficulty here is that sustainability definitions are all very concerned with the future, a future that we all are historically very bad at predicting: more so when, as sustainability practitioners often claim, the concern is with the future of all humanity everywhere on Earth.

We can choose to ignore fundamental critiques like (Eilenberger 2010) or (Treanor 1997), who consider sustainability as an essentially conservative ideology, desperately searching "for every possible argument against change in the existing political social, economic, cultural and technological order" (ibid.) But we cannot ignore that the right moment for a sustainability assessment never comes, because sustainability has no end moment. The bill is never settled, because in a sustainability perspective our human responsibility towards future humans (and, some would include, future entities of any type) never ends.

Some might see this as a guarantee of thoroughness and contrast it with the limited horizons of *efficiency*.

A few cases will suffice to show how the concept of sustainability, when used for evaluating anything in the real world, has to be either truncated temporally (so the evaluation stops abruptly at some future horizon) or interpreted as a form of conservatism that approves only of the absence of change.

BURKINA FASO STRING BEANS

The news that an Italian NGO helped farmers from Burkina Faso set up an export channel to Italy for string beans and other vegetables (Shalom 2007) should have been welcomed: after all, here was an

African country exporting one item, namely string beans in winter, for which there is actually a market - as opposed to guilt-driven projects or simple export of raw materials.

The sustainability of the project has been questioned (Rizzo 2007) on the basis of its carbon footprint (the string beans have to travel by airplane) and of its deleterious effects on Italian string beans farmers. We could sit down and do a thorough analysis of all that is entrained by this project, its effects on the Italian vegetable market, its carbon emissions and everything that is required according to a sustainability practitioner of your choice.

But how can we tell what effects this new project will have in the future? We can do that either by imposing some arbitrary temporal horizon that we feel is within the grasp of our prediction techniques, or by deciding to define sustainability as the achievement of some sort of steady state, where string beans growing and exporting could continue indefinitely.

The first choice is not compatible with accepted definitions of sustainability. The second choice does not tell us a lot that is interesting: because what human enterprise continues indefinitely? Historically companies, industries and trade networks have prospered and then disappeared, or changed because of many different causes. Unless we are prepared to say that strong aversion to change is a good design driver, sustainability is not a good tool for this case.

SOLAR POWERED LOCALLY PRODUCED LED LANTERNS

The story comes from CNN (CNN 2010), and it is a very exciting one: a young Kenyan has started making and distributing LED lanterns that are recharged by a solar panel. His objective is to provide an affordable light source for school-age children in villages. The LED lantern is charged by a recycled piece of solar panel and it is distributed to villagers¹. The designer of the lamp, Evans Wadongo, was chosen by CNN as one their ten Heros for 2010, and the story echoed around the web accompanied by enthusiastic reactions.

¹ More information at the project site: <http://sustainabledevelopmentforall.org/>

The project is certainly based on a neat idea, but then one fact emerges: manufacturing each lantern costs 25 USD. Contributions are asked to offset the production price so that the lantern becomes more affordable for villagers. If the design problem is “Children in villages do not have affordable and healthy light for studying in the evening”, we can see that Mr. Wadongo’s solution (solution W) is clearly worse than going to an online Chinese shop (solution C). Minimal research shows that similar lanterns are available for a consumer price of 15 USD including shipping: we could assume that for a bulk order the price could be much lower.

Ultimately, though, choosing between C and W means choosing between distributing a larger number of lanterns (solution C) and the possibility of bootstrapping a local light manufacturing and electronics industry (solution W) - in other words, two different models of development for Kenya. People that specialize in these extremely uncertain type of decision, with long-running consequences, no clear solution and social involvement on a large scale exist: but they are called politicians, not designers.

EFFICIENCY AND PRACTICES

We claim that sustainability is a bad design driver; but at the same time, we share a concern for the state of the world and the consequences of design. Such a concern can, as we have mentioned, be made operational by thinking in terms of *efficient practices*. Efficiency rates design solutions in terms of their resource consumption, **all other things being equal**. Efficiency thinking requires to define a boundary for the system being analyzed: inputs and outputs cross this border and they are measured to determine the efficiency of the system.

In a sustainability perspective, these borders cannot be effectively drawn.

Practices, defined by (Shove and Pantzar 2005) as “practices involve the active integration of materials, meanings and forms of competence.”, capture the fact that there are aspects of the relationship between user and product that go beyond acquisition, appropriation, use and disposal: a product has also a social side and plays a central part in the performance of social activities loaded with meaning.

Examples of practices include cooking, a practice-based discussion of which must include not only food, cooks, utensils and family members: but also the social and aspirational meaning of a certain type of kitchen, and the values embedded in cooking, for example as mediated by television shows (Shove, Watson et al. 2007).

Practices can provide the borders required by efficiency thinking; they offer a middle scale between large scale systemic thought and small scale classic industrial design thought founded on the relationship between the user and the product. (De Borja, Kuijer et al. 2010), for example, apply practice theory to design for sustainability: to reduce the environmental impact of meat consumption and waste in the Netherlands, their solution is to transform meat-eating from a frequent and unappreciated activity to one that is frequent and highly appreciated.

CONCLUSIONS

We have tried to show that sustainability is a bad choice for a design driver because it is poorly defined, it is founded on an exceptionalist view of an enchanted world, and it is very hard to use for inspiration or validation. Additionally, it easily leads into design conservatism. We have offered efficient practices as a usable middle ground between the global World system (too large) and classical industrial design relationship of user and product (too small).

REFERENCES

- Baker, S. (2006). Sustainable Development. New York, Routledge.
- Basalla, G. (1988). The evolution of technology, Cambridge Univ Press.
- Brundtland, G. H. (1987). Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: "our Common Future": Annex, United Nations.
- CNN. (2010, February 12, 2010). "'Saving lives' with solar-powered lights." February 12, 2010, <http://edition.cnn.com/2010/LIVING/02/11/cnnheroes.wadongo/index.html>.
- De Borja, J., L. Kuijter, et al. (2010). "Designing for sustainable food practices in the home."
- Edgerton, D. (2007). The shock of the old: technology and global history since 1900, Oxford University Press.
- Ehrenfeld, J. (2008). Sustainability by design: a subversive strategy for transforming our consumer culture, Yale University Press.
- Ehrlich, P. R. (1968). The population bomb, Sierra Club/Ballantine Books.
- Eilenberger, W. (2010). "Against Sustainability: On the new paradigm of the last humans." IP Global(November 2010).
- IUCN (1980). World conservation strategy: Living resource conservation for sustainable development. IUCN. Gland, Switzerland.
- Lomborg, B. (2001). "The skeptical environmentalist: measuring the real state of the world." Cambridge (UK): 165-172.
- Madge, P. (1997). "Ecological design: a new critique." Design Issues **13**(2): 44-54.
- Maslow, A. H., R. Frager, et al. (1987). Motivation and personality, Harper Collins: 293.
- Rizzo, S. (2007). Sinistra divisa sui «fagiolini equi» della Coop Corriere della Sera. Milan.
- Sanders, D. (2011). Arrival City: How the Largest Migration in History Is Reshaping Our World. New York, Pantheon.
- Schuler, D. and A. Namioka (1993). Participatory design: Principles and practices, CRC.
- Shalom. (2007, 18-1-2011). "I fagiolini del Burkina." Retrieved 11-5-2011, from <http://www.movimento-shalom.org/demo2/news.asp?id=127>.
- Shove, E. and M. Pantzar (2005). "Consumers, Producers and Practices: Understanding the invention and reinvention of Nordic walking." Journal of Consumer Culture **5**(1): 43-64.
- Shove, E., M. Watson, et al. (2007). The Design of Everyday Life. Oxford, Berg.
- Treanor, P. (1997, 1-12-1997). "Why Sustainability is 'wrong'." Retrieved 10-5-2011, 2011, from <http://web.inter.nl.net/users/Paul.Treanor/sustainability.html>.
- van der Sanden, M. C. A., Ed. (2007). You Can't Just Blame the Crocodile: Delft Engineers Travel Into Sustainability. Delft, Delft university of technology.
- Vinnerås, B., M. Hedenkvist, et al. (2009). "Peepoo bag: self-sanitising single use biodegradable toilet." Water science and technology: a journal of the International Association on Water Pollution Research **59**(9): 1743.

Figure 1. Dinner in a Bangkok railway slum. Who is going to say what are their "essential needs"?